

Supplementary Table ST3: Comparison of Deep Learning Architectures

Architecture	Key Characteristics	Strengths	Limitations	Representative Studies
LSTM / BiLSTM	future context	series; handles variable-length sequences	very long sequences;	S76, S92
CNN (including ConvLSTM)	Convolutional layers for spatial feature extraction; ConvLSTM extends to spatiotemporal	invariant; ConvLSTM captures spatial-	temporal dynamics;	S57, S85
Hybrid CNN-RNN	Combines CNN for spatial features with RNN/LSTM for temporal dependencies	effectively	complexity; two-stage	S75, S90
Transformers / Attention	Self-attention mechanisms; processes sequences in parallel; captures long-range dependencies	excellent for long sequences; attention	complexity O(L ²);	S40, S65, S93
Foundation Models	Large-scale pre-trained models (GraphCast, Pangu, FuXi, GenCast); fine-tuned for specific tasks	across tasks; fast inference	resources for training;	S31, S35, S71, S93
GANs / Generative AI	Generator-discriminator architecture; produces realistic synthetic samples	reduces blur in predictions; realistic spatial	collapse; hard to evaluate	S48, S60, S78, S86
Autoencoders (VAE)	Encoder-decoder for dimensionality reduction and feature learning	training; anomaly detection	reconstruction loss may	S27, S50, S78, S88
GNNs	Graph-based spatial relationships; handles irregular grids	flexible for complex geometries	requires domain expertise;	S6, S7, S77